

Possible Antiamoebic Agents. Part XIII. Synthesis of Substituted Quinoxalines

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Several substituted dihydroxy- and dimethoxy-quinoxalines have been prepared for studying their antiamoebic activity.

The amoebicidal activity of oxine and its derivatives is attributed by some workers to chelation with traces of polyvalent metals like iron or cobalt to form feebly dissociated complexes, which are toxic in nature (Albert *et al.*, *Med. J. Austral.*, 1944, 31, 245; *Brit. J. Exp. Path.*, 1947, 28, 69). Thompson *et al.* (*Amer. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1955, 4, 224) and Burkhalter *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4902) from their studies of halogenated 8-hydroxyquinolines have conclusively proved that chelation only is responsible for the amoebicidal activity of these compounds and not the presence of halogen atoms in them. These observations led us to synthesise derivatives of dihydroxyquinoxaline, which have two chelating centres in the molecule and should therefore be more active than oxine, if chelation is mainly responsible for amoebicidal activity.

The steps involved in the synthesis of 3-substituted-5,8-dihydroxyquinoxalines are given below.

Starting from hydroquinone, 1,4-dimethoxy-2,3-diaminobenzene was prepared by a 3-step synthesis according to Lester *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 1451). It was then condensed with ethyl oxomalonate in ethanol to yield 3-hydroxy-2-ethoxycarbonyl-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline (I), which was then refluxed with POCl_3 , whereby the -OH group in position 3 was replaced by a chlorine atom. The chloro compound, thus obtained, was hydrolysed by sodium carbonate in 75% ethanol to 3-chloro-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid. The acid was decarboxylated by heating it at its m.p. for 2 to 3 minutes to (IV). The 3-chloro-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline (IV) obtained was changed to 3-substituted-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline by the action of different amines in ethanol on (IV) in presence of calcined potassium carbonate. The dimethoxyquinoxalines were then hydrolysed with 48% hydrobromic acid to the corresponding dihydroxy derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

2,3-Diamino-1,4-dimethoxybenzene.—The starting material for this was 1,4-dimethoxybenzene, which was prepared from hydroquinone according to Dyson *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 440). It was nitrated in glacial acetic acid with fuming nitric acid in the cold (Habermann, *Ber.*, 1878, **11**, 1035; Nietzki and Reckberg, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 1215). The required 2,3-dinitro-1,4-dimethoxybenzene was isolated by fractional crystallisation of the nitrated product from ethyl acetate. This was reduced catalytically to the diamino compound in ethanol using platinum oxide as catalyst, following the method of Lester *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), m.p. 84-85° (Lester *et al.* record m.p. 85-87°).

3-Hydroxy-2-ethoxycarbonyl-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline (I).—As difficulties were encountered in the isolation of the free diaminodimethoxybenzene, it was directly condensed after reduction of 2,3-dinitro-1,4-dimethoxybenzene as follows. The dinitro compound (4.56 g., 0.02 *M*) was dissolved in ethanol (100 c.c.) and catalytically reduced in presence of platinum oxide. The catalyst was removed by filtration and the filtrate was mixed with ethyl oxomalonate (3.48 g., 0.02 *M*) ("Org. Synthesis", Vol. I, p. 261), and the mixture refluxed on a water bath for 4 hours. Yellow-green shining crystals separated on cooling, which were filtered and washed with little ethanol, m.p. 242°. (Found : N, 9.57. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.07%).

3-Chloro-2-ethoxycarbonyl-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline (II).—The compound (I, 5.5 g.) was heated with POCl_3 (30 c.c.) at 120-30° in an oil bath for 1 hour. Excess of POCl_3 was removed under reduced pressure and the residue decomposed with ice. The chloro compound was then extracted with ether and finally recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 154°, yield 5.4 g. (Found : N, 9.88. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 9.44%).

3-Hydroxy-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline-2-carboxylic Acid (VII).—The quinoxaline (II, 1.2 g.) was heated with 10% NaOH solution for 15 minutes, cooled, and acidified with HCl (dil.) to Congo red (according to a method of Gowenlock, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 623). A red compound was obtained, which was purified by dissolving it in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitating it with HCl (dil.), m.p. 213°, yield 0.9 g. (Found : N, 10.87. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$ requires N, 11.20%).

3-Chloro-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid (III) was prepared by hydrolysing a mixture of (II, 6.0 g.) with sodium carbonate (3.0 g.) in 200 c.c. of 75% ethanol on a water bath for 4 hours, following the method of Gowenlock (*loc. cit.*). Ethanol was removed and the residue was dissolved in water and acidified with HCl (dil.) to Congo red. An orange-coloured compound was obtained, which was further purified by dissolving it in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitating it with HCl (dil.), m.p. 168°, yield 5.0. (Found : N, 9.96. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 10.42%).

3-Chloro-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline (IV).—The above acid (III, 5.0 g.) was melted in a porcelain dish and the temperature was maintained for 2 to 3 minutes. After cooling it was extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the unchanged acid and filtered. The precipitate was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 128°, yield 3.4 g. (Found: N, 12.22. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 12.47%).

TABLE I

R ₃	Substituted quinoxalines.				Picrolonates.		
	M.P.	Yield.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
R ₅ & R ₆ = dimethoxy.							
Diethylaminopropylamino-	152°	31%	17.33	17.61	210-12°	18.91	19.24
Piperidinopropylamino-	146°	48	16.59	16.96			
Morpholinopropylamino-	153°	42	16.58	16.86	265°	18.32	18.79
Benzylamino-	138-39°	61	13.98	14.23			
Ethanolamino-	148°	57	16.42	16.86	300°	18.46	19.10
Glycino-	144°	69	15.54	15.96			
R ₅ & R ₆ = dihydroxy.							
Diethylaminopropylamino-	221°	69	18.82	19.31			
Piperidinopropylamino-	209-10°	83	18.11	18.54			
Morpholinopropylamino-	215°	92	18.07	18.42			
Benzylamino-	199°	94	15.26	15.73			
Ethanolamino-	196-97°	80	19.08	19.00			
Glycino-	151°	64	17.36	17.87			

3,5,8-Trihydroxyquinoxaline-2-carboxylic Acid (VIII).—The compound (I, 0.5 g.) was heated under reflux with 48% HBr (5 c.c.) for 15 minutes. It soon dissolved and then deposited red crystals after some times, which were filtered and washed with water. It dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with evolution of CO₂ showing thereby the presence of —COOH group formed by hydrolysis of the COOEt group of (I), m.p. 223°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: N, 12.19. $C_9H_6O_5N_2$ requires N, 12.61%). It was also obtained by hydrolysis of compound (VII) with HBr.

3-Chloro-5,8-dihydroxyquinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid (IX) was obtained by hydrolysis of both (II) and (III). Compound (II, 0.3 g.) was heated with 46% HBr (5 c.c.) till a red compound separated out (about ½ hour), which was then isolated in the usual way, m.p. 228°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: N, 11.50. $C_9H_5O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 11.64%).

3-Chloro-5,8-dihydroxyquinoxaline (X) was obtained by hydrolysis of (IV, 0.56 g.) with 48% HBr (5 c.c.) for 1 hour. After cooling, the mixture was neutralised with sodium carbonate solution and concentrated on a water bath almost to dryness. The residue was extracted with dry chloroform, the solvent removed, and the residue recrystallised from 95% ethanol, m.p. 211°, yield 0.4 g. (Found : N, 14.61. $C_8H_5O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 14.24%).

Dialkylaminoalkylamines were prepared by reduction of the corresponding dialkylamino-alkyl nitriles, following the method of Holcomb and Hamilton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1309).

3-Substituted-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxalines.—A mixture of 3-chloro-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline (0.005 M), the appropriate amino compound (0.005 M) in 50 c.c. ethanol, and calcined potassium carbonate (0.0025 M) was refluxed for 4 to 8 hours. Completion of the reaction was confirmed by a change of colour of the reaction mixture. Potassium chloride formed was filtered off, solvent removed, and the residue obtained was recrystallised from a suitable solvent. A few of the quinoxalines were characterised through their picrolonates (Table I).

3-Substituted-5,8-dihydroxyquinoxalines were prepared from 3-substituted 5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline (0.002 M) by hydrolysing with 48% HBr (5 c.c.) for 1 hour. After cooling it was neutralised with sodium carbonate solution. The solution was evaporated to dryness on a water bath and the dihydroxy compound extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was dried. The product obtained after removal of the solvent was recrystallised from ethanol.

The m.p., yields and analytical data of 3-substituted-5,8-dimethoxy- and -5,8-dihydroxyquinoxalines are reported in Table I.